

Automatic Question Paper Generator System

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ABSTRACT

Information and intelligence are two vital columns on which development of humankind rise and knowledge has significant impact on operating of society. Student assessment is a crucial part of teaching and is done through the process of examinations and preparation of exam question papers has consistently been a matter of interest. Present-day technologies assist the teacher to stock the questions in a computer databases but the problem which emerges is how the present day technologies would also assist the teachers to automatically create the variety sets of questions from every now and then without worry about replication and duplication from the previous exam while the question bank keeps growing.

KEYWORDS: Automatic test paper generator with shuffling algorithm, Automatic question paper generator system using randomization algorithm, Automatic question generation system

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INTRODUCTION

In today's current ambitious world, an examination plays a crucial role in checking the academic development of students and the era of information technology is now substituted by productive application of the technology. So producing utility from knowledge is crucial for development of society into an "Information Society". For various examinations conducted in a year in Any academic course, teachers need to create variation of question papers as per the autonomous college guidelines and assessment requirements. It is very difficult for the teachers to cover all features of the course outcomes and evade duplication of questions in the succeeding exams. There is no systematic procedure and hence the quality of the question paper relies entirely on an individual teacher's experience and proficiency.

Uses of Automatic Question Generator System:

The procedure involved in composition of an equitable examination paper by an independent is challenging and complex. Standard of the examination paper rely on diverse set of specifications so taking into account the distinct levels of learners is also a crucial parameter and the course outcomes also play a vital role in planning a systematic question paper. So associating the learning outcome of the subject to the examination paper is also a great job. Automatic creation of examination paper yields a stage to create a well-organized examination paper and also the automation would smooth in incorporating many elements determining quality of a question paper. The structure

presented in the next module is to automate the activity of examination paper generation. This generic structure can be redesigned to all departments in colleges thus ease the assessment needs. Before the exam could be given to the student, teachers must compose the questions according to the modules covered for individual subject. A proficient question paper is habitually fit for usual students but it also encloses demanding items for clever students. Thus automatically creating question paper from a teacher's entered description using a semantically labeled question bank is the requirement of the hour in present day. Here we are implementing a system which accordingly creates the question paper from this semantically labeled question bank.

Functions of Automatic Question Paper Generator System:

In this assessment they can used the different kinds of modules for preparing question paper automatically. When creating question paper from a teacher's entered description using a semantically labeled question bank is the requirement of the hour in present day. Here we are implementing a system which accordingly creates the question paper from this semantically labeled question bank. Since the prevailing systems are stiff and absence of flexibility of aiding all types of labels, the produced question paper may not be completely range with its given outcomes. Our each stuff is defined with a range demonstrating that value should not be under the bottom value and not surpass the topmost value of the range. Also, it is rule base system

which takes all the associations of the labels and creates solution based on the rule relevant.

Advantages:

- The system has several advantages to teachers compare to manual system.
- System can generate question randomly.
- Save time in preparing question paper for the examination.
- It is made to allow university to generate question papers with random but even questions to cover most chapters of subject with difficulty level within seconds and mail them to colleges instantly.
- We also allow admin to provide weight age and complexity for each of these questions.
- The questions are also added for various difficulty levels so that as soon admin chooses the type of paper difficulty (Easy, medium, difficult) the system automatically generates paper.

Why we need?

In the existing system the college staffs only generate the questions. The staffs not generate the questions in randomly. It makes staff to easily prepare question papers in randomly. It can be safe and secured. Only staff can access these system and also they have separate login id & password to set the question papers. In these system a staff can choose the question paper various difficulty level.

Conclusion :

Hence there appears a requirement to have a system which will automatically create the question paper from teacher entered description within few seconds. In this paper we

have implemented a modern evolutionary path that is able to manage multi-constraints issue along with creating question papers for examinations in autonomous institutes from a very vast question bank database. This paper describes the utilization of randomization algorithm in an Automatic Question paper Generator System which has been implemented specially for autonomous institutes. The endeavor needed for generating question paper is diminished after the implementation of this advanced system and because of this advanced system there is no obligation for humans to ponder and employ time which can be utilized on some additional important duty instead of designing question paper.

References:

- [1] Yang Yu, Hongyan Wang, Adaptive Online Exam Questions Based on Systematic Analysis and Design, vol. 4, Wuhan University of Technology, 2008, p. 3 Google Scholar
- [2] Binghua Chen B/S Model of Building a Test Server, vol. 08, China's Information Technology Education(2008), p. 87 View Record in Scopus
- [3] Gui Wang JSP-Based Platform for Remote Examination of The Design and Implementation, vol. 10, Mobile office (2008), p. 41 CrossRefView Record in Scopus
- [4] Bing Liu **Developers Surprise Java Web** Publishing House of Electronics Industry, Beijing (2008) Google Scholar
- [5] R. Johnson, J. Hoeller **Expert One-on-one J2EE Development Without EJB[M]** Wiley Publishing Inc., Indianapolis (2004) Google Scholar.s

